

A Sieve Method for Generating 1+1 Prime Pairs and Goldbach Function

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Abstract

A 2-step sieve method for generating **1+1** prime pairs, satisfying Goldbach's conjecture that every even integer greater than 2 can be written as the sum of two primes, has been disclosed. By direct counting based on indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the so-called Goldbach function, **G(2n)**, which is the number of distinct ways **2n** can be expressed as the sum of two prime numbers, for a positive integer **n** is generated accordingly. The result is

$$\mathbf{G}(2n) \sim (n-1)[(3-2)/(3-1)][(5-2)/(5-1)] \dots [(\mathbf{p}_x-2)/(\mathbf{p}_x-1)](1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5) \dots [1-1/(\mathbf{p}_y)] \times \mathbf{F}_{cg}(n),$$
 where $\mathbf{p}_x \sim n^{1/2}$, $\mathbf{p}_y \sim (2n)^{1/2}$, and $\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n)$ is a function defined as follows:

$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n)=1$, if there is no prime number \mathbf{p} , $2 < \mathbf{p} \leq \mathbf{p}_x$, such that $n \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$;

$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n) = [(\mathbf{p}_a-1)/(\mathbf{p}_a-2)] [(\mathbf{p}_b-1)/(\mathbf{p}_b-2)] [(\mathbf{p}_c-1)/(\mathbf{p}_c-2)] \dots$, if there are distinct prime numbers $\mathbf{p}_a, \mathbf{p}_b, \mathbf{p}_c, \dots$, $2 < \mathbf{p}_a < \mathbf{p}_b < \mathbf{p}_c < \dots \leq \mathbf{p}_x$, such that $n \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_a}$, $n \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_b}$, $n \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_c} \dots$

When **2n** is very large,

$\mathbf{G}(2n) \sim 2\mathbf{C}\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n) \times n/[\ln(2n)]^2$, or

$$\mathbf{G}(2n) \sim 2\mathbf{C}\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n) \times \int_2^n \frac{1}{[\ln(s)]^2} ds + 1$$

where $\mathbf{C} \sim 0.660162$ is Hardy–Littlewood's twin prime constant.

G(2n) is a local peak when **n** contains more different prime factors which are less than $n^{1/2}$. For example, $\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n) > \mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n \pm 2) \geq 1$, and, thus, $\mathbf{G}(2n) > \mathbf{G}(2n \pm 2)$ when $n = \mathbf{p}_a \mathbf{p}_b \mathbf{p}_c \dots$. The peak distribution can explain the so-called Goldbach's comet.^[1]

If \mathbf{G}_{avg} is the average of **G(2n)** over a range of **2n** values, then

$\mathbf{G}_{avg} \sim (2\mathbf{C}/\mathbf{K}) \times n/[\ln(2n)]^2$, where $\mathbf{K} < 1$ is a constant depending on the local peaks in the range, and

$\mathbf{G}(2n)/\mathbf{G}_{avg} \sim \mathbf{K}\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n) = \mathbf{K}[(\mathbf{p}_a-1)/(\mathbf{p}_a-2)] [(\mathbf{p}_b-1)/(\mathbf{p}_b-2)] [(\mathbf{p}_c-1)/(\mathbf{p}_c-2)] \dots$, where $2 < \mathbf{p}_a < \mathbf{p}_b < \mathbf{p}_c < \dots < n^{1/2}$ are the distinct prime factors of **n**. This is similar to the result published by Hardy and Littlewood.^[2]

Since $n \gg [\ln(2n)]^2$ & $\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2n) \geq 1 \Rightarrow \mathbf{G}(2n) \gg 1$ for a large **2n** even number, there exists at least a pair of primes such that **2n** is the sum of these two primes. This is also true for every small $2n > 2$ by inspection or direct calculation without mathematical approximations. Therefore, every even integer greater than 2 can be written as the sum of two primes.

I. Introduction

Goldbach's conjectured that every integer greater than 2 can be written as the sum of two primes. The conjecture has often been referred as one prime plus one prime conjecture, or **1+1** conjecture. So far, it seems that there has been no complete proof of this conjecture. The closest proof was reported by J. R. Chen in 1973 that a larger even integer could be the sum of a prime and the product of at most two primes.^[3]

In this paper, a 2-step sieve method for generating **1+1** prime pairs, satisfying Goldbach's conjecture that every even integer $2n > 2$ can be written as the sum of two primes, has been disclosed. With indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the so-called Goldbach function, $\mathbf{G}(2n)$, or the number of the **1+1** prime pairs for $2n > 2$, is generated accordingly. The derived $\mathbf{G}(2n)$ has shown many local peaks that can explain the so-called Goldbach's comet.^[1]

II. Sieve Method for Generating 1+1 Prime Pairs for $2n$

For an even integer $2n > 2$ to be written as the sum of two primes, the two primes must be of the forms $n+m$ & $n-m$, where n & m are integers satisfying $0 \leq m \leq n-2$. The first step of the sieve method is to preclude non-prime numbers in the interval $[n, 2n-2]$ by sifting all the $n-1$ values with a sieve similar to those of the prior publications^{[4],[5]} to remove all $n+m$ values that are in the residue class of $(0 \pmod{p})$ for each prime p , $2 \leq p \leq p_y \sim (2n)^{1/2}$. All the $n+m$ values left after removing are all primes.

For a set $\mathbf{S} = \{n | n \text{ is a natural number, and } 1 \leq n \leq N_n\}$, and $N_n = p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$, where $2 = p_1 < p_2 < p_3 < p_4 < \dots < p_w$ are consecutive prime numbers, every number n in \mathbf{S} has a unique residue vector with respect to moduli $(p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, \dots, p_w)$ according to indication of the Chinese remainder theorem. There are total of $N_n = p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$ residue vectors. After removing n numbers that belong to a residue class of each prime number up to p_w , there are exactly $N_r = (p_1-1)(p_2-1)(p_3-1)(p_4-1)\dots(p_w-1)$ residue vectors left, representing the number of elements left from \mathbf{S} . Thus, the ratio of the number of elements left to the original number of total elements in \mathbf{S} is

$$\mathbf{N}_r/\mathbf{N}_n = (p_1-1)(p_2-1)(p_3-1)(p_4-1)\dots(p_w-1)/(p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w) = (1-1/p_1)(1-1/p_2)(1-1/p_3)(1-1/p_4)\dots(1-1/p_w)$$

If N_n is a multiple of $p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$, the above equation is the exact ratio of N_r/N_n . Otherwise, it is an approximation. Thus, by direct counting based on the indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the number of the $n+m$ values left after sieving is:^[5]

$$\mathbf{G}_1(2n) \sim (n-1) \times (1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5)\dots(1-1/p_y) \quad (1)$$

These $\mathbf{G}_1(2n)$ values of $n+m$ belong to $p-1$ residue classes, without $(0 \pmod{p})$, of each prime p , $2 \leq p \leq p_y \sim (2n)^{1/2}$. For $n > 2$, $p_y \sim (2n)^{1/2} < n$. Thus, there is no prime $n+m$ values removed by the first sieve step.

The second step of the sieve method is to preclude the corresponding $n-m$ values in the residue class $(0 \pmod{p})$ for $2 < p \leq p_x$. There is no need to preclude with $p=2$ since $n-m \equiv n+m \pmod{2}$. The only pairs

containing 2 is when $2n=4=2+2$. If there is no prime number p , $2 < p \leq p_x \sim n^{1/2}$, such that $n \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, the corresponding $G_I(2n)$ values of $n-m$ also belong to $p-1$ residue classes, but including residue class $(0 \pmod{p})$ of each prime p , $2 \leq p \leq p_x$. The second step is to remove those $n-m$ values that satisfies $n-m \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Thus, one more residue class is precluded from the existing $p-1$ residue classes, and the number of $n-m$ values after the second step is

$$G_{II}(2n) \sim G_I(2n) \times \left[\frac{(3-2)}{(3-1)} \right] \left[\frac{(5-2)}{(5-1)} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(p_x-2)}{(p_x-1)} \right] \\ \sim (n-1) \times \left[\frac{(3-2)}{(3-1)} \right] \left[\frac{(5-2)}{(5-1)} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(p_x-2)}{(p_x-1)} \right] \times (1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5) \dots (1-1/p_y) \quad (2)$$

There are $G_{II}(2n)$ prime pairs of the form $n+m$ & $n-m$. It needs to be cautious that $G_{II}(2n)$ might be less than the Goldbach function, $G(2n)$, which is the number of distinct ways $2n$ can be expressed as the sum of two prime numbers $n+m$ & $n-m$, since some of the small $n-m$ prime values are also removed in the second step.^[5] Therefore,

$$G(2n) = G_{II}(2n) + s_p(2n) \\ \sim (n-1) \times \left[\frac{(3-2)}{(3-1)} \right] \left[\frac{(5-2)}{(5-1)} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(p_x-2)}{(p_x-1)} \right] \times (1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5) \dots (1-1/p_y) + s_p(2n), \quad (3)$$

where $s_p(2n)$ is the numbers of small $n-m$ primes that are removed during the second sieve step.^[5]

For a very large n ,

$$n-1 \sim n, \quad (4)$$

$$\ln(2n) = \ln(2) + \ln(n) \sim \ln(n), \quad (5)$$

$$\left[\frac{(3-2)}{(3-1)} \right] \left[\frac{(5-2)}{(5-1)} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(p_x-2)}{(p_x-1)} \right] \\ = \left[\frac{(3-2)}{3} \right] \left[\frac{(5-2)}{5} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(p_x-2)}{p_x} \right] \left[\frac{2}{(2-1)} \right]^{-1} \left[\frac{2}{(2-1)} \right] \left[\frac{3}{(3-1)} \right] \left[\frac{5}{(5-1)} \right] \dots \left[\frac{p_x}{(p_x-1)} \right] \\ \sim 4C [\ln(n)]^{-2} \times (1/2) \ln(n) = 2C [\ln(n)]^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

where $C \sim 0.660162$ is Hardy–Littlewood's twin prime constant.

$$(1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5) \dots [1-1/(p_y)] \sim [\ln(2n)]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Combining Eqs. (3)-(7), $G(2n)$ becomes

$$G(2n) \sim 2C \times n / [\ln(2n)]^2 + s_p(2n) \quad (8)$$

If $2n$ increased by a relatively small even number dn ,

$$G(2n+dn) \sim 2C \times (n+dn) / [\ln(2n+dn)]^2 + s_p(2n+dn), \text{ and}$$

$$G(2n+dn) - G(2n) \sim 2C \times dn / [\ln(2n)]^2 \text{ since } \ln(2n+dn) \sim \ln(2n) \text{ \& } s_p(2n+dn) \sim s_p(2n).$$

By integrating the two sides, a more accurate expression for $G(2n)$ without neglecting $s_p(2n)$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n}) \sim 2\mathbf{C} \times \int_2^{\mathbf{n}} \frac{1}{[\ln(\mathbf{s})]^2} d\mathbf{s} + 1 \quad (9)$$

If there are distinct prime numbers $\mathbf{p}_a, \mathbf{p}_b, \mathbf{p}_c, \dots, 2 < \mathbf{p}_a < \mathbf{p}_b < \mathbf{p}_c < \dots \leq \mathbf{p}_x$, such that $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_a}$, $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_b}$, $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_c} \dots$, then

$$\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_a} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} - \mathbf{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_a},$$

$$\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_b} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} - \mathbf{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_b},$$

$$\mathbf{n} + \mathbf{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_c} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} - \mathbf{m} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_c},$$

.....

There is no need for the second step to remove the corresponding $\mathbf{n} - \mathbf{m}$ values in residue classes $(0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_a})$, $(0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_b})$, $(0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_c}) \dots$. For correction, a function, $\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n})$, is defined as follows:

$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n}) = 1$ if there is no prime number \mathbf{p} , $2 < \mathbf{p} \leq \mathbf{p}_x$, such that $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$;

$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n}) = \frac{(\mathbf{p}_a - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_a - 2)} \frac{(\mathbf{p}_b - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_b - 2)} \frac{(\mathbf{p}_c - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_c - 2)} \dots$ if there are distinct prime numbers $\mathbf{p}_a, \mathbf{p}_b, \mathbf{p}_c, \dots, 2 < \mathbf{p}_a < \mathbf{p}_b < \mathbf{p}_c < \dots \leq \mathbf{p}_x$, such that $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_a}$, $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_b}$, $\mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_c} \dots$

Thus, $\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n})\mathbf{G}_{II}(2\mathbf{n}) + \mathbf{s}_p(2\mathbf{n})$, and Eq. (3) becomes

$$\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n}) \sim (\mathbf{n} - 1) \frac{(3 - 2)}{(3 - 1)} \frac{(5 - 2)}{(5 - 1)} \dots \frac{(\mathbf{p}_x - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_x - 2)} (1 - 1/2)(1 - 1/3)(1 - 1/5) \dots [1 - 1/(\mathbf{p}_y)] \times \mathbf{F}_{cg}(\mathbf{n}) + \mathbf{s}_p(2\mathbf{n}) \quad (10)$$

Neglecting $\mathbf{s}_p(2\mathbf{n})$ for a very large \mathbf{n} , $\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n})$ in Eq. (8) becomes

$$\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n}) \sim 2\mathbf{C}\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n}) \times \mathbf{n} / [\ln(2\mathbf{n})]^2 \quad (11)$$

The more accurate expression, Eq. (9), for $\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n})$ without neglecting $\mathbf{s}_p(2\mathbf{n})$ becomes

$$\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n}) \sim 2\mathbf{C}\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n}) \times \int_2^{\mathbf{n}} \frac{1}{[\ln(\mathbf{s})]^2} d\mathbf{s} + 1 \quad (12)$$

Eqs. (11) & (12) are similar to those conjectured in the past.

$\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n})$ is a local peak when \mathbf{n} contains more distinct prime factors which are less than $\mathbf{n}^{1/2}$. For example, $\mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n}) > \mathbf{F}_{cg}(2\mathbf{n} \pm 2) \geq 1$, and, thus, $\mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n}) > \mathbf{G}(2\mathbf{n} \pm 2)$ when $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{p}_a \mathbf{p}_b \mathbf{p}_c \dots$. The peak distribution can explain the so-called Goldbach's comet.^[1] The significant impacts are from those small prime factors. For example,

$$\frac{(\mathbf{p}_a - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_a - 2)} = 2 \text{ for } \mathbf{p}_a = 3,$$

$$\frac{(\mathbf{p}_b - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_b - 2)} = 4/3 \text{ for } \mathbf{p}_b = 5,$$

$$\frac{(\mathbf{p}_c - 1)}{(\mathbf{p}_c - 2)} = 6/5 \text{ for } \mathbf{p}_c = 7,$$

....., and

$$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(6) = 2,$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(10) = 4/3,$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{cg}(14) = 6/5,$$

$F_{cg}(30)=8/3,$
 $F_{cg}(42)=12/5,$
 $F_{cg}(70)=8/5,$
 $F_{cg}(210)=16/5, \dots, \text{etc.}$

If G_{avg} is the average of $G(2n)$ over a range of $2n$ values, then

$G_{avg} \sim (2C/K) \times n / [\ln(2n)]^2$, where $K < 1$ is a constant depending on the local peaks in the range, and

$G(2n)/G_{avg} \sim KF_{cg}(2n) = K[(p_a-1)/(p_a-2)] [(p_b-1)/(p_b-2)] [(p_c-1)/(p_c-2)] \dots$, where $2 < p_a < p_b < p_c < \dots < n^{1/2}$ are the distinct prime factors of n . This is similar to the result disclosed by Hardy and Littlewood.^[2]

III. Conclusion and Discussion

Since $n \gg [\ln(2n)]^2$ & $F_{cg}(2n) \geq 1 \Rightarrow G(2n) \gg 1$ for a large $2n$ even number, there exists at least a pair of primes such that $2n$ is the sum of these two primes. This is also true for every small $2n > 2$ by direct inspection or calculation without mathematical approximations. Thus, every even integer greater than 2 can be written as the sum of two primes.

The sieve procedure can also be sifting $n-m$ values first and then sifting the corresponding $n+m$ ones. In this case, the value of $s_p(2n)$ could possibly be larger, but the results for large n values are about the same.

Similar to the sieve methods for generating prime k -tuples,^[5] it's intriguing that the derived Goldbach function results, by direct counting based on indication of the Chinese remainder theorem without conjectures, seem to match well with those of the prior conjectures based on probabilities and complex methods.^{[1],[2]}

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V. Reference

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